

A Case Study in Strict-FIFO UTXO Taint Propagation:

The 2010 Pizza-Day Transaction Through Depth 5

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Abstract

The canonical 10,000 BTC Pizza-Day purchase on 22 May 2010 is one of the most frequently cited and least forensically analysed events on the Bitcoin blockchain. Prior treatments surveyed here either trace from the sender’s address rather than the recipient’s or stop at two degrees of separation; mainstream coverage stops at the counterfactual valuation. This case study walks the descendant transaction graph of transaction `a1075db5...d48d` under three explicit taint conventions (strict positional FIFO, proportional haircut, and poison) through a depth-5 horizon, and audits where the conventions agree and where they diverge. The contribution is a reproducible methodological case study: every pruning rule, fee-absorption bucket, and processed artifact is made explicit, so that any reader can re-run the analysis under an alternative taint convention and obtain a comparable answer. Two chain-only observations follow directly from the trace: (i) the two FIFO-tainted branches that fed the 2010-07-07 consolidation event had each been dormant for ≈ 45 days beforehand, and (ii) one address (`18ZChq...`) appears both as a depth-2 successor of the 5,777 BTC pizza half and as a counterparty to three of four lifetime transactions of the consolidation address (`1PrwYM...`). Convention choice changes aggregate horizon attribution by 11.77 % between FIFO and poison; per-branch attribution can shift more, with the largest branch rising from 4,500 BTC under FIFO to 5,677 BTC under poison (a 26 % relative shift) while the visited topology is unchanged at the 1 BTC dust threshold. Under strict positional FIFO with the named 1 BTC dust threshold, the depth-5 horizon, and a one-step frontier outspend check, the traced frontier contains no uniquely identifiable dormant Pizza-Day UTXO; each horizon UTXO was itself further spent in the next transaction beyond the cutoff.

Keywords: Bitcoin, UTXO, taint analysis, forensic accounting, chain analysis, FIFO, reproducibility, Pizza Day.

1 Introduction

Bitcoin uses an unspent-transaction-output (UTXO) ledger model. A transaction consumes one or more existing UTXOs and produces new ones; outputs are not labelled by their origin, and there is no canonical mapping from input satoshis to output satoshis. The question “*where are the bitcoins that paid for the pizza?*” therefore has no unique answer after the first hop. Any forensic claim about the present-day location of those satoshis presupposes a taint convention, which is rarely stated.

This paper picks one convention — *strict positional FIFO* — and applies it to the canonical descendant graph of the 22 May 2010 transaction in which Laszlo Hanyecz paid 10,000 BTC to a recipient known as `jercos` (Jeremy Sturdivant) for two Papa John’s pizzas. The contribution is not the convention — positional FIFO over UTXO indices is one of several established choices in the chain-analysis literature, with Anderson et al. [1] offering an explicit legal-doctrine grounding via Clayton’s Case — but the worked artefact: a depth-5 trace whose code, dataset, and sensitivity to convention choice are public.

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Scope. Single canonical transaction. Strict positional FIFO as the primary convention, with FIFO/haircut/poison comparison at the horizon. Depth-5 cutoff with explicit fee-absorbed and dust-pruned terminals. mempool.space block-explorer data, cached locally, with the chain tip height recorded for reproducibility.

Out of scope. Legal identity claims, off-chain corroboration beyond what is publicly archived on bitcointalk.org, multi-case generalisation, cluster heuristics beyond the input-count threshold.

Contributions.

- A reproducible depth-5 strict-FIFO descendant graph of the canonical Pizza-Day transaction, with conservation invariant *algorithmically* enforced via a fee-absorbed terminal.
- A sensitivity comparison across the three established taint conventions (FIFO, haircut, poison) showing where they agree and where they diverge.
- Two chain-only observations derived from the trace: a 45-day dormancy between the depth-2 18ZChq. . . hop and the depth-3 consolidation (an observation derivable from any public block explorer; the convention machinery does not contribute to deriving it), and an address-overlap signal linking a descendant node to the consolidation address counterparty set (a suggestive coincidence, not benchmarked against a matched-sample base rate).
- An explicit four-layer evidence ladder (chain fact / convention / behavioral inference / narrative) intended to discipline future single-case forensic claims.

2 Background

2.1 The UTXO ledger and taint conventions

In the UTXO model a transaction’s outputs are unsigned amounts payable to specified scripts. Spending an output consumes it entirely; partial spends are achieved by sending the remainder as a change output. Each UTXO is uniquely identifiable on the ledger by its (txid, vout) pair, but the satoshis it contains are not labelled by their input origin and no per-satoshi mapping from input to output is encoded. Bitcoin is thus unit-fungible in the economic sense (any one satoshi is interchangeable with any other) while being lot-distinguishable at the ledger layer (each UTXO is a uniquely addressable lot). Any per-satoshi identification scheme that traverses a transaction is therefore a *convention* layered on top of the ledger rather than a property the ledger guarantees. Three conventions are common in the chain-analysis literature:

FIFO (strict positional). Each input is modelled as a value range whose first `taint` satoshis are tainted and the remaining `value - taint` are clean. Outputs are filled left-to-right; for each input we donate its tainted portion first, then its clean portion. Anderson et al. [1] argued that this maps onto the rule from *Devaynes v. Noble* (1816), commonly cited as *Clayton’s Case*, a Court of Chancery decision on tracing fungible money through mixed bank accounts.¹ It is also important that this is *positional* FIFO over UTXO indices within the input vector, which is only a structural analogue — not a literal restatement — of the *temporal* FIFO Clayton’s Case applies to deposit sequences: the chain has no time-of-deposit signal within a single transaction. The construction is lossless in a way poison and haircut are not.

¹The rule’s scope has been substantially limited by subsequent equity doctrine, notably *In re Hallett’s Estate* [5] and *Barlow Clowes International Ltd v. Vaughan* [2], and English courts now treat it as a default that can be displaced where its application would be impractical or unjust. Recent UK case law on cryptocurrency tracing (*D’Aloia v. Persons Unknown* [3]) treats FIFO as a mechanical Clayton’s Case method while recognising that non-FIFO approaches may be available where they are properly evidenced. We use FIFO here as algorithmic discipline, not as binding legal mapping.

Haircut (proportional). The tainted fraction T/V of the inputs applies uniformly to every output. Output i receives $\lfloor v_i \cdot T/V \rfloor$ of taint; whatever portion of the inbound taint does not land on an explicit output — on the canonical Pizza-Day data this is dominated by integer-floor rounding because the consolidation transaction paid zero fee, but in general it includes the proportional share of any non-zero miner fee — is absorbed into the fee-taint bucket.

Poison (maximalist). If any input is tainted, every output is treated as fully tainted. The taint pool can grow as clean descendants merge into already-tainted transactions; the method is an upper bound, never a lower one.

Tironsakkul et al. [11] evaluate poison, haircut, FIFO, and proposed order/value-based variants on theft cases, and treat precision and accuracy as an open measurement problem rather than as settled empirical rankings. Meiklejohn et al. [6] pioneered the empirical clustering and graph-tracing methodology underlying most subsequent work; their paper received the IMC Test-of-Time Award in 2024.

2.2 Related work: prior coverage of the Pizza-Day transaction

The transaction `a1075db5...d48d` (block 57043, 22 May 2010 at 18:16 UTC) appears in dozens of articles and several academic treatments. Reid and Harrigan [10] produced one of the first network-level analyses of Bitcoin and visualised high-throughput addresses but did not specifically isolate the Pizza-Day descendants. Möser et al. [8] catalogued mixing services and AML countermeasures in the early ecosystem. Moussa and Cuzzocrea [9] present a data-warehouse model of Bitcoin transactions and use the Pizza-Day transaction as their primary worked example, captioned as “*131 input addresses participated in the pizza transaction*”. The transaction in fact has 131 *inputs* consolidated from a single sending address; we correct that misreading in section 5.

The closest precedent for descendant tracing of the Pizza-Day transaction is Allen Day’s 2018 Google Cloud notebook, which queries the public BigQuery Bitcoin dataset and visualises a two-degree neighbourhood around Hanyecz’s *sending* address. Because the seed is the sender, that visualisation aggregates every outgoing transaction Hanyecz made during the surrounding period, not the Pizza-Day descendants specifically. The present paper traces from the recipient’s output forward.

3 Methodology

The full code and configuration live in the public repository <https://github.com/mnardit/pizza-day-trace>; the README and `METHODOLOGY.md` document every pruning decision in prose. The present section makes the algorithmic invariants explicit.

3.1 Topological ordering

Descendant transactions are processed in chain-topological order: (*block_height, in_block_position*). The in-block position is resolved via the explorer’s `block_txids/` endpoint and the transaction’s index inside the returned canonical list.

If a transaction is not present in its expected block (reorg, cache, or API inconsistency), the `tx_position_in_block` routine raises `TxPositionLookupError` rather than degrading silently to a sentinel position. Within each spending transaction, taint is distributed under the configured convention (FIFO by default), and the *taint* residue not consumed by explicit outputs lands in a *fee-absorbed* terminal bucket. This guarantees the conservation invariant

$$\sum_{\text{outputs}} \text{taint}_i + \text{fee_taint} = \sum_{\text{inputs}} \text{taint}_j$$

algorithmically rather than empirically, for the FIFO and haircut conventions. The poison convention is non-conserving by construction — clean inputs joining a tainted transaction inflate

the taint pool — and the invariant is therefore enforced and tested only on FIFO and haircut runs; the poison output is reported as an upper bound, never as a conserved attribution.

3.2 Pruning rules

Each terminal classification is a stop-condition the trace records when it decides to stop following a UTXO. They are not forensic conclusions about the destination of the satoshis.

- **dust-pruned**: a UTXO is recorded as terminal when its tainted amount falls below 1 BTC. This is a project budget threshold, not a Bitcoin policy dust threshold. On the Pizza-Day data this threshold is three orders of magnitude below every per-output tainted amount under every convention and never binds; it is documented here for repeatability and for re-use on datasets where it would.
- **cluster-absorbed**: when a tainted UTXO is consumed by a transaction with ≥ 100 inputs, the spending transaction is treated as a cluster boundary and the tainted inputs are recorded as cluster-absorbed. The 100-input figure is an empirical round-number choice rather than a theoretically grounded boundary; chain-analysis firms typically use cluster heuristics with different (often proprietary) input thresholds. On this dataset the boundary is also inert: no tainted UTXO within depth 5 is consumed by a transaction with ≥ 100 inputs.
- **depth-pruned**: at depth 5, all remaining tainted UTXOs are recorded as horizon terminals without further tracing.
- **still-unspent**: the UTXO has never been spent on the chain.
- **fee-absorbed**: the convention assigned taint to the implicit fee remainder rather than to any explicit output.

4 Data and snapshot

All on-chain data is fetched through the mempool.space REST API [7] and cached locally in `data/cache.sqlite`. The cache is gitignored, but every committed processed artifact carries provenance metadata so a reader can distinguish a true reproduction (re-deriving from the cache) from a fresh API query that may pick up new content (in particular, the recipient address still receives small dust deposits, which would alter later runs of the recipient-afterlife analysis).

The snapshot used in this paper has the following provenance:

- Chain tip at trace time: block height **949,941** (`mempool.space /blocks/tip/height`).
- Repository state used for submission: `c75f255` (full SHA on the public repo at <https://github.com/mnardit/pizza-day-trace>). The trace computation provenance recorded inside `headline-summary.json` is the squash-init commit `d45a1edb4066bdf35d918eb0046fb383f2246cc5`. Numerical trace outputs (`utxo-tree.csv`, `conventions-comparison.json` numbers, `anchor-inputs.csv`, `jercos-deposits.csv`) are unchanged between the two commits; only metadata wording and the test-suite documentation were updated subsequently.
- Python version: 3.12.3.
- Pinned dependency manifest: `requirements-lock.txt` in the repo.
- Processed artifacts used:
 - `utxo-tree.csv`
 - `anchor-inputs.csv`
 - `jercos-deposits.csv`
 - `conventions-comparison.json`
 - `headline-summary.json`

What can change on future reruns: the recipient address’s deposit history may grow as new dust arrives, and mempool.space response ordering for paginated address queries is not strictly archival. Both are constrained by the chain-tip pin: any future deposit beyond block 949,941 lies outside this paper’s snapshot.

5 The anchor transaction

The anchor is transaction `a1075db55d416d3ca199f55b6084e2115b9345e16c5cf302fc80e9d5fbf5d48d`, included in block 57043 at 18:16:31 UTC on 22 May 2010 (block timestamp; **14:16 ET**, not 1:16 PM ET as it appears in one frequently-cited CoinDesk piece — May was in Eastern Daylight Time). It has 131 *inputs* (not 131 input addresses, as [9] captions) and a single 10,000 BTC output to address `17SkEw2md5avVnyYgj6RiXuQKNwkXaxFyQ`, the recipient `jercos`. All 131 inputs come from the single sending address `1XPTgDRhN8RFnznIWCddobD9iKZatrVH4`, publicly self-attributed by Hanyecz on bitcointalk thread #137 [4]; the trace treats this self-attribution as a chain-external behavioral signal, not a chain fact.

The input composition is striking. Of the 131 inputs, 111 are exactly 0.01 BTC — *crumbs* from earlier consolidations and small payments. The remaining 20 are chunkier: one piece of 3,753.88 BTC (carrying 37.5% of the value Hanyecz needed) and 19 pieces in the 50–900 BTC range. The largest piece had been held at the sending address for only 5.2 days; the mean age across all 131 inputs was 30.7 days. Total input value is 10,000.99 BTC; the difference of 0.99 BTC went to the miner of block 57043 as fee. By 2010 norms the fee was large — most transactions paid none — but in 2010 dollars its value was sub-cent: at the late-May 2010 USD/BTC range of roughly \$0.003–\$0.008 quoted on Bitcoin Market and the earliest exchanges, the 0.99 BTC fee corresponds to a small fraction of a US cent.²

6 The descendant graph

6.1 Topology and timing

Under strict positional FIFO at the 1 BTC dust threshold and the depth-5 horizon, the descendant graph contains 10 distinct UTXOs across 7 distinct transactions. Figure 1 renders the full topology; the paragraphs below describe it in chronological order.

Same-day movement (22 May 2010). Ten minutes after the anchor, in block 57044, `jercos` spent the full 10,000 BTC, splitting it into 5,777 BTC at `1MLh2...` and 4,223 BTC at a P2PK output with no encoded address. Forty-seven minutes later, in block 57053, the 5,777 BTC half moved one further hop to `18ZChqRsb7eKgH8wLg9Pfkkezux34pf6eo`. Both halves then sat.

The 45-day dormancy. For 45 days and approximately 8 hours, neither half moved on chain.

Consolidation (7 July 2010). At 02:56 UTC on 2010-07-07, in block 64683, a single transaction (`9e744590...dd1957`) absorbed both halves alongside 18 other UTXOs of non-pizza-tainted provenance into one 11,022 BTC output at address `1PrwYMffhu1XJyVXs6Ba67NidGZVjbGHCq`. Of the 11,022 BTC, the strict-FIFO convention attributes exactly 10,000 BTC of pizza-taint and 1,022 BTC of non-pizza-tainted change. The fee paid by this consolidation transaction was zero. One position later in the same block, the 11,022 BTC was spent again into two outputs of 5,500 and 5,522 BTC.

²The same fee restated at mid-2026 BTC/USD quotations (\sim \$77 000/BTC) is on the order of USD 76–77 000. We flag the discrepancy explicitly because that retrospective valuation is the same move the popular Pizza-Day coverage performs on the 10,000 BTC principal and which this paper otherwise treats as a category error: a 2010 fee is properly priced in 2010 USD; the 2026 figure is a counterfactual, not a market price.

Figure 1: Descendant UTXO graph from the Pizza-Day anchor under strict positional FIFO at the 1 BTC dust threshold, traversed to depth 5. Edges represent “UTXO consumed by transaction that produced child UTXO”. Node labels show UTXO value in BTC; where value and FIFO taint differ, the tainted BTC is shown in parentheses. Depth-5 frontier nodes are dashed; each was itself further spent in the next transaction beyond the horizon, but that one-step lookup is not part of the recursive trace and does not appear as an edge in the graph.

Tail and horizon. Seven minutes later, the 5,522-BTC chain (1NX8uq . . . , 4,500 BTC of taint) made one more hop into a 5,677-BTC UTXO at 1KcAt5 . . . , carrying the 4,500 BTC of taint forward. Six days, fourteen hours later, the 5,500-BTC chain (1B7cet . . . , fully tainted) split into 3,500 and 2,000-BTC UTXOs. At depth 5 the trace stops on three frontier UTXOs holding 4,500, 3,500, and 2,000-BTC of strict-FIFO pizza-taint respectively, summing to exactly the original 10,000 BTC. Their next-hop spending status, checked one step beyond the horizon without further recursion, is *spent* for all three:

Table 1: Depth-5 frontier UTXOs and their immediate next-hop status, checked one transaction beyond the horizon (not a continued recursive trace). Trace stopped at the depth cutoff, not at an observed dormancy. “Spent” in the next-hop column means the frontier UTXO was itself consumed in a subsequent transaction; this paper makes no claim about the topology or attribution beyond depth 6.

UTXO (txid:vout)	Address	Tainted BTC	UTXO value	Next-hop
7f02e1a8...90b2:0	1KcAt5...	4,500	5,677	spent
6ac97d58...61fa:0	12ofyF...	3,500	3,500	spent
6ac97d58...61fa:1	17G2pj...	2,000	2,000	spent

6.2 Linked-address observation

The address 18ZChqRsb7eKgH8wLg9Pfkkezux34pf6eo is the depth-2 successor of the 5,777 BTC pizza half. It is also a counterparty in three of the four lifetime transactions of the depth-3 consolidation address 1PrwYM...

- 2010-05-22 19:13 UTC — the consolidation address receives 250 BTC *from* 18ZChq...
- 2010-05-22 19:28 UTC — the consolidation address sends 250 BTC *back* to 18ZChq...
- 2010-07-07 02:56 UTC — the consolidation address receives 11,022 BTC, partly from 18ZChq... (the 5,777 BTC pizza half) and partly from another sender.

The 250-BTC out-and-back pattern can be described, post hoc, as wallet-test-like, and is consistent with common or coordinated control of the two addresses; however, this is a descriptive label, not a validated heuristic, and the trace does not on its own establish either that control regime or any verification purpose. It is one of several behaviorally plausible readings — alternative routine explanations include a wallet-software change-handling artifact or an unrelated counterparty interaction — and *not* an identity proof. We make no claim about Sturdivant’s legal identity, about the legal relationship of 18ZChq... to either Hanyecz or jercos, and no allegation that any party to this trace acted unlawfully or improperly.

We also do not quantify a null hypothesis for the co-occurrence. The denominator is itself shaped by the same flow (two of the consolidation address’s four lifetime transactions are the matched 250-BTC out-and-back pair), and the calculation has not been benchmarked against a matched-sample base rate of co-occurrences for 2010-era four-lifetime-tx addresses. Treating this as a suggestive on-chain coincidence rather than a statistically discriminating signal is appropriate, and quantifying the false-positive rate is left as future work.

7 Sensitivity to taint convention

We re-ran the trace under all three conventions while keeping every other parameter fixed (depth 5, 1 BTC dust prune, 100-input cluster threshold).

Table 2: Sensitivity of horizon attribution to taint convention.

Convention	Horizon BTC tainted	Fee-absorbed (BTC)	Largest tainted branch
FIFO (strict positional)	10,000.00	0	4,500 at 1KcAt5...
Haircut (proportional)	9,999.999 999 98	0.000 000 02	5,009.98 at 1KcAt5...
Poison (maximalist)	11,177.00	0	5,677 at 1KcAt5...

The three conventions agree on the visited topology (the same 10 UTXOs across the same 7 transactions) because the 1 BTC dust-pruning threshold is below every per-output tainted amount. Raising the dust-pruning threshold for a fixed convention prunes *more*, not fewer, branches; the convention-comparison consideration is relative: because the poison convention

attributes greater taint to each output than FIFO or haircut, branches that FIFO and haircut prune at a given threshold may still be visited under poison at the same threshold. Aggregate horizon attribution differs by 11.77% between FIFO and poison; per-branch attribution can shift more — the largest branch rises from 4,500 BTC under FIFO to 5,677 BTC under poison, a 26% relative shift — and that is precisely the disagreement any present-tense claim about “the pizza bitcoins” typically hides.

8 Discussion

8.1 Evidence ladder

We summarise the kinds of claim this trace can support, in decreasing order of evidential strength:

Table 3: Evidence ladder for forensic claims about the Pizza-Day descendants. As a rough guide to evidential strength only: *chain fact* is technical record evidence; *tracing convention* layered onto chain fact yields a technical attribution model whose legal sufficiency depends on the forum, remedy, evidentiary record, and corroboration, and may not survive without independent off-chain support (*cf. D’Aloia v. Persons Unknown* [3], which recognised FIFO as a relevant method but cautioned against reliance on a single chronological-sequence approach); *behavioral inference* is usually legally fragile without corroborating off-chain evidence; *narrative* carries no on-chain support and is included only to mark the boundary.

Layer	Example from this trace	Strength
Chain fact	cca7507... spends 10,000 BTC into two new outputs.	hard
Tracing convention	Strict FIFO assigns 5,500 BTC tainted to the first depth-4 output.	methodological
Behavioral infer.	18ZChq... appearing in both flows is consistent with common or coordinated control.	probabilistic
Narrative claim	jercos funded a road trip with the proceeds.	unsupported on chain

Most coverage of the Pizza-Day transaction lives in the bottom two rows and presents them with the confidence of the top row.

8.2 What the trace can and cannot prove

The supported claim is narrow: under strict positional FIFO, a 1 BTC dust prune, a 100-input cluster boundary, and a depth-5 horizon (with chain tip pinned in `headline-summary.json`), the trace finds no uniquely identifiable dormant Pizza-Day UTXO at the frontier. We note the one-step frontier outspend lookup uses depth-6 information that the recursive trace itself does not visit; the frontier-spent result therefore relies on a single additional chain query per UTXO, and is reported separately from the trace topology to keep the depth-5 horizon discipline clean. The trace does not establish satoshi identity after spending, the recipient’s legal identity, the legal relationship between any of the involved addresses, or an exhaustive characterisation of descendants beyond depth 5; nor does the absence of a dormant horizon UTXO imply the satohis were converted to fiat, since dispersion below the dust threshold, on-chain re-mixing, third-party custody, and key loss are all equally consistent with that observation.

8.3 What we deliberately do not do

We do not de-anonymise clusters past widely-known endpoints. We do not trace past depth 5 because the signal-to-noise ratio after five hops is poor and we keep the horizon explicit. We do not trace Hanyecz’s other known pizza payments (he made several); only the canonical transaction is in scope.

9 Limitations

- **Single-case design.** One canonical transaction; no cross-validation against other historical UTXO trees.
- **Convention sensitivity is bounded, not closed.** We compare FIFO, haircut, and poison. Other conventions (LIFO, coinage-weighted, taintchain) exist and would yield different per-output attributions.
- **Pruning thresholds are budgets.** A different dust cutoff or cluster boundary would visit a different subset of the descendant graph. For a fixed convention, a higher dust cutoff prunes more aggressively. The relevant convention-comparison observation is relative: at thresholds at which FIFO and haircut prune a branch, the same branch may remain under poison because poison attributes more taint to each output.
- **No external clustering.** We do not invoke chain-analysis firm address graphs or off-chain reputation data. The linked-address signal is a chain-only co-occurrence; it cannot establish legal identity.
- **No claim of present-tense location.** The trace ends at depth 5; the frontier outspend lookup is a one-step extension, not an exhaustive forward trace. We make no claim about descendant satoshi positions after the horizon.
- **Public-API dependence.** mempool.space response ordering is not strictly archival. The cache pin and chain-tip snapshot mitigate this but do not eliminate it.
- **Poison is non-conserving.** The poison convention inflates attributed taint when clean inputs join a tainted transaction. We label this explicitly; readers seeking conservation invariants should restrict attention to FIFO and haircut.

10 Reproducibility

The companion repository <https://github.com/mnardit/pizza-day-trace> contains:

- the Python implementation of the tracer (`src/tracer.py`),
- the explorer client with SQLite cache (`src/explorer.py`),
- the convention comparison runner (`src/run_conventions.py`),
- committed processed datasets under `data/processed/`,
- 20 invariant tests under `tests/`,
- a pinned dependency lock-file (`requirements-lock.txt`),
- a GitHub Actions workflow that runs the tests on push.

The `headline-summary.json` artifact records the chain tip height at trace time, the repository commit SHA, and the Python version under which the pipeline was last run, so re-runners can distinguish “I reproduced the computation” from “I asked the public API again.”

11 Conclusion

The interesting question turned out not to be where the pizza coins went. It was what happens when one takes the casual phrase “*those bitcoins*” seriously and tries to follow them on the chain. Within a few hops one is no longer following coins; one is following *taint under a chosen convention*. The descendant graph is real, but which fraction of which output one calls “*pizza-tainted*” depends on a choice made before the trace began. Strict positional FIFO gives one set of numbers; poison gives another; haircut yet another. None is canonical at the ledger level; each answers a different attribution question, and none is the chain “*saying so.*”

The single canonical Pizza-Day transaction was an unusually good test case for this disciplining: it has a well-defined anchor, a small descendant graph at depth 5, and a media coverage that almost universally elides the convention question. Under the named FIFO convention, the 1 BTC dust threshold, the depth-5 horizon, and a one-step frontier check, the trace finds no uniquely identifiable dormant Pizza-Day UTXO at the frontier; the three horizon UTXOs were themselves further spent in the next transaction beyond the cutoff. The trace does not, and cannot from a single-case chain-only analysis, characterise the full descendant population beyond that frontier. The methodological lesson generalises: *any* present-tense claim about the location of a historical UTXO’s descendants is properly read with both its convention and its horizon named.

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Figure 2 caption (“131 input addresses participated in the pizza transaction”) is corrected in the present paper’s anchor analysis: 131 inputs, one sending address.

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